

Supplementary Information

***In silico* exploration of graphene nanoflakes: From DFT simulations to machine learning-driven toxicity predictions**

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Table S1. Total number of carbons (nC) and hydrogen (nH) atoms, shape (HEX: hexagonal, RECT: rectangular and TRI: triangular), type of edge (ARM: armchair and ZIG: zigzag) and dimensions, of each of the 98 graphene nanoflakes studied in this work. L , l indicates de largest and smallest dimensions, respectively.

Graphene nanoflake	nC	nH	Shape	Edge_1	Edge_2	Size / Å	
						L	l
HEX_ARM_C42H18	42	18	HEX	ARM	ARM	13.5	11.8
HEX_ARM_C84H24	84	24	HEX	ARM	ARM	17.8	16.7
HEX_ARM_C222H42	222	42	HEX	ARM	ARM	30.6	26.5
HEX_ZIG_C24H12	24	12	HEX	ZIG	ZIG	9.3	9.2
HEX_ZIG_C54H18	54	18	HEX	ZIG	ZIG	14.2	13.5
HEX_ZIG_C96H24	96	24	HEX	ZIG	ZIG	19.1	17.8
HEX_ZIG_C150H30	150	30	HEX	ZIG	ZIG	24.1	22.1
HEX_ZIG_C216H36	216	36	HEX	ZIG	ZIG	29.0	26.3
RECT_zz2ac2_C16H10	16	10	RECT	ZIG	ARM	8.0	7.1
RECT_zz2ac4_C28H14	28	14	RECT	ZIG	ARM	11.4	8.0
RECT_zz2ac6_C40H18	40	18	RECT	ZIG	ARM	15.8	8.0
RECT_zz2ac8_C52H22	52	22	RECT	ZIG	ARM	20.1	8.0
RECT_zz2ac10_C64H26	64	26	RECT	ZIG	ARM	24.4	8.0
RECT_zz2ac12_C76H30	76	30	RECT	ZIG	ARM	28.7	8.0
RECT_zz2ac14_C88H34	88	34	RECT	ZIG	ARM	33.0	8.0
RECT_zz2ac16_C100H38	100	38	RECT	ZIG	ARM	37.3	8.0
RECT_zz2ac18_C112H42	112	42	RECT	ZIG	ARM	41.6	8.0
RECT_zz2ac20_C124H46	124	46	RECT	ZIG	ARM	45.9	8.0
RECT_zz2ac22_C136H50	136	50	RECT	ZIG	ARM	50.2	8.0
RECT_zz2ac24_C148H54	148	54	RECT	ZIG	ARM	54.5	8.0
RECT_zz2ac26_C160H58	160	58	RECT	ZIG	ARM	58.8	8.0
RECT_zz2ac28_C172H62	172	62	RECT	ZIG	ARM	63.2	8.0
RECT_zz2ac30_C184H66	184	66	RECT	ZIG	ARM	67.5	8.0
RECT_zz2ac32_C196H70	196	70	RECT	ZIG	ARM	71.8	8.0
RECT_zz4ac2_C28H14	28	14	RECT	ZIG	ARM	12.9	7.2
RECT_zz4ac4_C48H18	48	18	RECT	ZIG	ARM	12.9	11.5
RECT_zz4ac6_C68H22	68	22	RECT	ZIG	ARM	15.8	12.9
RECT_zz4ac8_C88H26	88	26	RECT	ZIG	ARM	20.1	12.9
RECT_zz4ac10_C108H30	108	30	RECT	ZIG	ARM	24.4	12.9
RECT_zz4ac12_C128H34	128	34	RECT	ZIG	ARM	28.7	12.9
RECT_zz4ac14_C148H38	148	38	RECT	ZIG	ARM	32.9	13.0
RECT_zz4ac16_C168H42	168	42	RECT	ZIG	ARM	37.2	13.0
RECT_zz4ac18_C188H46	188	46	RECT	ZIG	ARM	41.5	13.0
RECT_zz4ac20_C208H50	208	50	RECT	ZIG	ARM	45.7	13.0
RECT_zz4ac26_C268H62	268	62	RECT	ZIG	ARM	58.6	13.0
RECT_zz4ac28_C288H66	288	66	RECT	ZIG	ARM	62.9	13.0
RECT_zz6ac2_C40H18	40	18	RECT	ZIG	ARM	17.8	7.2
RECT_zz6ac4_C68H22	68	22	RECT	ZIG	ARM	17.8	11.5
RECT_zz6ac6_C96H26	96	26	RECT	ZIG	ARM	17.9	15.8
RECT_zz6ac10_C152H34	152	34	RECT	ZIG	ARM	24.3	17.9
RECT_zz6ac12_C180H38	180	38	RECT	ZIG	ARM	28.6	17.9
RECT_zz6ac14_C208H42	208	42	RECT	ZIG	ARM	32.9	17.9
RECT_zz6ac16_C236H46	236	46	RECT	ZIG	ARM	37.2	17.9
RECT_zz6ac18_C264H50	264	50	RECT	ZIG	ARM	41.5	17.9
RECT_zz8ac2_C52H22	52	22	RECT	ZIG	ARM	22.7	7.2
RECT_zz8ac4_C88H26	88	26	RECT	ZIG	ARM	22.8	11.5
RECT_zz8ac6_C124H30	124	30	RECT	ZIG	ARM	22.8	15.8
RECT_zz8ac8_C160H34	160	34	RECT	ZIG	ARM	22.8	20.1
RECT_zz8ac10_C196H38	196	38	RECT	ZIG	ARM	24.3	22.8
RECT_zz8ac12_C232H42	232	42	RECT	ZIG	ARM	28.6	22.8
RECT_zz8ac14_C268H46	268	46	RECT	ZIG	ARM	32.8	22.8
RECT_zz10ac2_C64H26	64	26	RECT	ZIG	ARM	27.6	7.2
RECT_zz10ac4_C108H30	108	30	RECT	ZIG	ARM	27.7	11.5
RECT_zz10ac6_C152H34	152	34	RECT	ZIG	ARM	27.7	15.8

RECT_zz10ac8_C196H38	196	38	RECT	ZIG	ARM	27.7	20.1
RECT_zz10ac10_C240H42	240	42	RECT	ZIG	ARM	27.7	24.3
RECT_zz10ac12_C284H46	284	46	RECT	ZIG	ARM	28.6	27.7
RECT_zz12ac2_C76H30	76	30	RECT	ZIG	ARM	32.5	7.2
RECT_zz12ac4_C128H34	128	34	RECT	ZIG	ARM	32.6	11.5
RECT_zz12ac6_C180H38	180	38	RECT	ZIG	ARM	32.6	15.8
RECT_zz12ac8_C232H42	232	42	RECT	ZIG	ARM	32.6	20.1
RECT_zz12ac10_C284H46	284	46	RECT	ZIG	ARM	32.6	24.3
RECT_zz14ac2_C88H34	88	34	RECT	ZIG	ARM	37.4	7.2
RECT_zz14ac4_C148H38	148	38	RECT	ZIG	ARM	37.5	11.5
RECT_zz14ac6_C208H42	208	42	RECT	ZIG	ARM	37.5	15.8
RECT_zz14ac8_C268H46	268	46	RECT	ZIG	ARM	37.5	20.1
RECT_zz16ac2_C100H38	100	38	RECT	ZIG	ARM	42.3	7.2
RECT_zz16ac4_C168H42	168	42	RECT	ZIG	ARM	42.4	11.5
RECT_zz16ac6_C236H46	236	46	RECT	ZIG	ARM	42.4	15.8
RECT_zz18ac2_C112H42	112	42	RECT	ZIG	ARM	47.2	7.2
RECT_zz18ac4_C188H46	188	46	RECT	ZIG	ARM	47.3	11.5
RECT_zz18ac6_C264H50	264	50	RECT	ZIG	ARM	47.4	15.8
RECT_zz20ac2_C124H46	124	46	RECT	ZIG	ARM	52.1	7.2
RECT_zz20ac4_C208H50	208	50	RECT	ZIG	ARM	52.2	11.5
RECT_zz20ac6_C292H54	292	54	RECT	ZIG	ARM	52.3	15.8
RECT_zz22ac2_C136H50	136	50	RECT	ZIG	ARM	57.0	7.2
RECT_zz22ac4_C228H54	228	54	RECT	ZIG	ARM	57.2	11.5
RECT_zz24ac2_C148H54	148	54	RECT	ZIG	ARM	61.9	7.2
RECT_zz24ac4_C248H58	248	58	RECT	ZIG	ARM	62.0	11.5
RECT_zz26ac2_C160H58	160	58	RECT	ZIG	ARM	66.8	7.2
RECT_zz26ac4_C268H62	268	62	RECT	ZIG	ARM	67.0	11.5
RECT_zz28ac2_C172H62	172	62	RECT	ZIG	ARM	71.7	7.2
RECT_zz28ac4_C288H66	288	66	RECT	ZIG	ARM	71.9	11.5
RECT_zz30ac2_C184H66	184	66	RECT	ZIG	ARM	76.6	7.2
RECT_zz32ac2_C196H70	196	70	RECT	ZIG	ARM	81.6	7.2
TRI_ARM_C36H18	36	18	TRI	ARM	ARM	13.6	11.8
TRI_ARM_C60H24	60	24	TRI	ARM	ARM	17.9	15.5
TRI_ARM_C90H30	90	30	TRI	ARM	ARM	22.1	19.2
TRI_ARM_C126H36	126	36	TRI	ARM	ARM	26.4	22.9
TRI_ARM_C168H42	168	42	TRI	ARM	ARM	30.7	26.6
TRI_ARM_C216H48	216	48	TRI	ARM	ARM	35.0	30.3
TRI_ZIG_C22H12	22	12	TRI	ZIG	ZIG	9.3	9.2
TRI_ZIG_C46H18	46	18	TRI	ZIG	ZIG	14.2	13.5
TRI_ZIG_C78H24	78	24	TRI	ZIG	ZIG	19.1	17.8
TRI_ZIG_C118H30	118	30	TRI	ZIG	ZIG	24.0	22.0
TRI_ZIG_C166H36	166	36	TRI	ZIG	ZIG	28.9	26.3
TRI_ZIG_C222H42	222	42	TRI	ZIG	ZIG	33.8	30.6
TRI_ZIG_C286H48	286	48	TRI	ZIG	ZIG	38.8	34.8

Table S2. BIOVIA Materials Studio descriptors chosen for the 98 GNFs.

<u>Atom Volumes and Surfaces</u>	<u>VAMP Electrostatics</u>
Connolly surface area	Total energy
Connolly surface occupied volume	Electronic energy
Solvent surface area	Heat of formation
Solvent surface occupied volume	HOMO eigenvalue
<u>Atomistic Descriptors</u>	LUMO eigenvalue
Total molecular mass	Molecular surface area
Atom count	Molecular point group
Element count	Total dipole
<u>DMol3 Molecular</u>	Dipole x
Total energy	Dipole y
Binding energy	Dipole z
HOMO energy	Quadrupole xx
LUMO energy	Quadrupole xy
LUMO-HOMO energy	Quadrupole yy
Total dipole	Quadrupole xz
Dipole x	Quadrupole yz
Dipole y	Quadrupole zz
Dipole z	Octupole xxx
Dielectric energy	Octupole xxy
Solvation energy	Octupole xxz
Surface area	Octupole xyy
Cavity volume	Octupole xyz
<u>Forcite Energetics</u>	Octupole xzz
Total energy	Octupole yyy
Non bond energy	Octupole yyz
van der Waals energy	Octupole yzz
<u>Spatial Descriptors</u>	Octupole zzz
Molecular area	Total ZDO dipole
Molecular volume	ZDO Dipole x
Molecular density	ZDO Dipole y
Principal moments of inertia	ZDO Dipole z
Principal moment of inertia X	Mean polarizability
Principal moment of inertia Y	
Principal moment of inertia Z	
Radius of gyration	
Ellipsoidal volume	
Shadow area: XY plane	
Shadow area: YZ plane	
Shadow area: ZX plane	
Shadow area fraction: XY plane	
Shadow area fraction: YZ plane	
Shadow area fraction: ZX plane	
Shadow length: LX	
Shadow length: LY	
Shadow length: LZ	
Shadow ratio	

Table S3. Human proteins (100) considered in this work.

<i>Family</i>	<i>PID</i>	<i>Family</i>	<i>PID</i>
ANTITUMOR	2rmn	METAL BINDING	2kax
	1o9k	MONOOXYGENASE	5pah
	2o2m		1r9o
APOPTOSIS	2ac0		4gqs
	1e31		4xrz
	1ao6		2hi4
CARRIER	4oeo		3gph
CELL ADHESION	1p53		3gzo
CHROMOSOMAL COMPLEMENT	1ubq		1dgf
	1gkg	OXIDOREDUCTASE	1d7w
	1m8a		3b96
1i1b	1u3u		
CYTOKINE	5m2m		6daq
	1il8		5I01
	1msg		4fr8
ELECTRON TRANSPORT	5z62		2z5y
HORMONE	1fzv		1ba9
	6gnq		5te8
	1gqs	OXYGEN STORAGE/TRANSPORT	2h35
	1p0p		1ro5
	1owe		4fl5
	4gwc	SIGNALING	2mgs
	4c6i		4g5q
	3lii		6pxw
	2c2m	STUCTURAL	6v5v
HYDROLASE	2pm8	TRANSCRIPTION	1svc
	4zcg		4dm4
	2glq		3w8q
	1m6d		2e9n
	1yk8		2nzt
	1r6h		4fsm
	3kme		3i5z
	4gqq		2wzb
	1l6j		4g1n
	4glr		5ikp
	4tqe	TRANSFERASE	1oth
IMMUNE SYSTEM	5d14		4ijq
	3oxs		3ie3
	4mhe		2avd
	4fm9		4ic8
ISOMERASE	1ek5		4x90
	4zvj		4ez3
LIPID BINDING	1g5w		2xir
	2b3x		2zb2
LYASE	5d6b		2jk4
	4fpt		6pzt
LIGASE (CARBOXYLATE)	2hgs	TRANSPORT	5eqg
	6agf		6c0v
	7e1z		4act
MEMBRANE	6irg		4act
	2znt		

Table S4. 33 GNFs (Column I) used for pre-processing, model optimization, and training of Random Forest predictive models; 7 GNFs (Column II) used for testing the performance of the models.

I. Graphene flake (training set)	II. Graphene flake (testing set)
HEX_ARM_C42H18	HEX_ZIG_C54H18
HEX_ARM_C84H24	HEX_ZIG_C96H24
HEX_ZIG_C24H12	RECT_zz2ac4_C28H14
HEX_ZIG_C150H30	RECT_zz6ac12_C180H38
RECT_zz2ac2_C16H10	RECT_zz8ac4_C88H26
RECT-zz4ac2-C28H14	TRI_ARM_C60H24
RECT-zz4ac4-C48H18	TRI_ARM_C90H30
RECT-zz4ac10-C108H30	
RECT-zz4ac18-C188H46	
RECT-zz6ac2-C40H18	
RECT_zz6ac6_C96H26	
RECT_zz6ac16_C236H46	
RECT-zz8ac2-C52H22	
RECT-zz8ac8-C160H34	
RECT-zz10ac2-C64H26	
RECT-zz10ac6-C152H34	
RECT-zz12ac2-C76H30	
RECT-zz12ac4-C128H34	
RECT-zz14ac2-C88H34	
RECT-zz14ac6-C208H42	
RECT-zz16ac2-C100H38	
RECT-zz18ac2-C112H42	
RECT-zz20ac2-C124H46	
RECT-zz22ac2-C136H50	
RECT-zz24ac2-C148H54	
RECT-zz26ac2-C160H58	
RECT-zz28ac2-C172H62	
RECT-zz30ac2-C184H66	
RECT-zz32ac2-C196H70	
TRI_ARM_C36H18	
TRI_ARM_C216H48	
TRI_ZIG_C22H12	
TRI_ZIG_C46H18	

Table S5. Intensities, in km/mol, and its infrared frequencies, in cm^{-1} , predicted for the most relevant vibrational modes, calculated with wB97x/def2-TZVP for three GFNs – HEX_ZIG_C54H18, RECT_zz2ac4_C28H14 and TRI_ARM_C60H24 –, sampling the types three shapes (HEX, RECT and TRI), the two types of edges (ARM, ZIG) and different sizes (42, 72 and 82 atoms). The scaling factor applied is 1.0. The final Gibbs free energy, in Eh, calculated as $G = H - T*S$, for these three GFNs is also reported.

GFN	Mode	Frequency / cm^{-1}	Intensity / km.mol^{-1}	Gibbs / Eh
HEX_ZIG_C54H18	56	623.05	39.79	-2068.54
	80	834.20	92.57	
	102	973.42	172.55	
	129	1199.60	16.41	
	130	1200.12	17.15	
	145	1328.47	24.90	
	146	1329.62	25.76	
	195	1696.40	15.83	
	196	1696.53	15.03	
RECT_zz2ac4_C28H14	38	678.93	16.48	-1075.30
	45	792.42	22.07	
	48	831.30	27.73	
	54	901.41	105.68	
	56	913.08	45.78	
	97	1486.21	32.46	
	106	1655.87	18.60	
TRI_ARM_C60H24	48	478.98	14.66	-2300.70
	93	814.93	152.79	
	98	848.75	88.77	
	104	871.40	112.73	
	168	1314.55	22.07	
	169	1316.02	21.78	
	183	1395.81	15.04	
	193	1481.33	17.57	
	194	1482.29	16.98	
	198	1503.57	21.23	
	199	1503.88	21.77	
	201	1533.03	34.14	
	202	1534.21	33.95	

Table S6. Docking mean (100 considered proteins) binding affinity and standard deviation of the protein – graphene flakes interaction per carbon atom in flake.

Graphene flake	<i>nC</i>	<i>Binding affinity / kcal·mol⁻¹</i>	<i>Standard deviation / kcal·mol⁻¹</i>
HEX_ARM_C42	42	-0.3	0.0
HEX_ARM_C84	84	-0.2	0.0
HEX_ARM_C222	222	-0.1	0.0
HEX_ZIG_C24	24	-0.4	0.1
HEX_ZIG_C54	54	-0.2	0.0
HEX_ZIG_C96	96	-0.2	0.0
HEX_ZIG_C150	150	-0.1	0.0
RECT_zz2ac2_C16	16	-0.5	0.1
RECT_zz2ac4_C28	28	-0.4	0.0
RECT_zz4ac2_C28	28	-0.4	0.1
RECT_zz4ac4_C48	48	-0.3	0.0
RECT_zz4ac10_C108	108	-0.2	0.0
RECT_zz4ac18_C188	188	-0.1	0.0
RECT_zz6ac2_C40	40	-0.3	0.0
RECT_zz6ac6_C96	96	-0.2	0.0
RECT_zz6ac12_C180	180	-0.1	0.0
RECT_zz6ac16_C236	236	-0.1	0.0
RECT_zz8ac2_C52	52	-0.3	0.0
RECT_zz8ac4_C88	88	-0.2	0.0
RECT_zz8ac8_C160	160	-0.1	0.0
RECT_zz10ac2_C64	64	-0.2	0.0
RECT_zz10ac6_c152	152	-0.1	0.0
RECT_zz12ac2_C76	76	-0.2	0.0
RECT_zz12ac4_C128	128	-0.2	0.0
RECT_zz14ac2_C88	88	-0.2	0.0
RECT_zz14ac6_C208	208	-0.1	0.0
RECT_zz16ac2_C100	100	-0.2	0.0
RECT_zz18ac2_C112	112	-0.1	0.0
RECT_zz20ac2_C124	124	-0.1	0.0
RECT_zz22ac2_C136	136	-0.1	0.0
RECT_zz24ac2_C148	148	-0.1	0.0
RECT_zz26ac2_C160	160	-0.1	0.0
RECT_zz28ac2_C172	172	-0.1	0.0
RECT_zz30ac2_C184	184	-0.1	0.0
RECT_zz32ac2_C196	196	-0.1	0.0
TRI_ARM_C36	36	-0.3	0.0
TRI_ARM_C60	60	-0.2	0.0
TRI_ARM_C90	90	-0.2	0.0
TRI_ARM_C216	216	-0.1	0.0
TRI_ZIG_C22	22	-0.4	0.1
TRI_ZIG_C46	46	-0.3	0.0
TRI_ZIG_C118	118	-0.2	0.0

Table S7. Free energy of penetration, per carbon atom in flake, through the four types of membranes considered in this work – DMPC, DOPC, POPC and SOPC – calculated at the center of the membrane for graphene flakes.

Structure	<i>n</i> C	DMPC	DOPC	POPC	SOPC
		$\Delta G / \text{kcal mol}^{-1}$	$\Delta G / \text{kcal mol}^{-1}$	$\Delta G / \text{kcal mol}^{-1}$	$\Delta G / \text{kcal}$
HEX_ARM_C42H18	42	-0.26	-0.26	-0.26	-0.27
HEX_ARM_C84H24	84	-0.25	-0.25	-0.24	-0.24
HEX_ZIG_C24H12	24	-0.30	-0.29	-0.30	-0.30
HEX_ZIG_C54H18	54	-0.26	-0.26	-0.26	-0.26
HEX_ZIG_C96H24	96	-0.25	-0.25	-0.24	-0.24
HEX_ZIG_C150H30	150	-0.23	-0.24	-0.22	-0.22
RECT_zz2ac2_C16H10	16	-0.32	-0.32	-0.32	-0.32
RECT_zz2ac4_C28H14	28	-0.29	-0.29	-0.29	-0.29
RECT_zz4ac2_C28H14	28	-0.30	-0.30	-0.30	-0.30
RECT_zz4ac4_C48H18	48	-0.27	-0.27	-0.27	-0.27
RECT_zz4ac10_C108H30	108	-0.23	-0.24	-0.22	-0.22
RECT_zz4ac18_C188H46	188	-0.18	-0.19	-0.18	-0.17
RECT_zz6ac2_C40H18	40	-0.29	-0.29	-0.29	-0.29
RECT_zz6ac6_C96H26	96	-0.24	-0.25	-0.24	-0.24
RECT_zz6ac12_C180H38	180	-0.19	-0.22	-0.19	-0.19
RECT_zz6ac16_C236H46	236	-0.18	-0.20	-0.18	-0.17
RECT_zz8ac2_C52H22	52	-0.28	-0.29	-0.28	-0.27
RECT_zz8ac4_C88H26	88	-0.25	-0.26	-0.24	-0.24
RECT_zz8ac8_C160H34	160	-0.17	-0.18	-0.17	-0.16
RECT_zz10ac2_C64H26	64	-0.27	-0.29	-0.27	-0.26
RECT_zz10ac6_C152H34	152	-0.20	-0.22	-0.19	-0.19
RECT_zz12ac2_C76H30	76	-0.26	-0.28	-0.26	-0.25
RECT_zz12ac4_C128H34	128	-0.21	-0.23	-0.21	-0.21
RECT_zz14ac2_C88H34	88	-0.25	-0.27	-0.25	-0.25
RECT_zz14ac6_C208H42	208	-0.07	-0.10	-0.06	-0.06
RECT_zz16ac2_C100H38	100	-0.24	-0.26	-0.24	-0.24
RECT_zz18ac2_C112H42	112	-0.23	-0.26	-0.23	-0.23
RECT_zz20ac2_C124H46	124	-0.22	-0.25	-0.22	-0.22
RECT_zz22ac2_C136H50	136	-0.22	-0.24	-0.22	-0.21
RECT_zz24ac2_C148H54	148	-0.21	-0.23	-0.21	-0.21
RECT_zz26ac2_C160H58	160	-0.21	-0.23	-0.21	-0.21
RECT_zz28ac2_C172H62	172	-0.19	-0.21	-0.19	-0.19
RECT_zz30ac2_C184H66	184	-0.19	-0.21	-0.19	-0.19
RECT_zz32ac2_C196H70	196	-0.19	-0.21	-0.19	-0.19
TRI_ARM_C36H18	36	-0.29	-0.29	-0.29	-0.29
TRI_ARM_C60H24	60	-0.27	-0.27	-0.27	-0.27
TRI_ARM_C90H30	90	-0.25	-0.26	-0.25	-0.25
TRI_ARM_C216H48	216	-0.21	-0.22	-0.21	-0.20
TRI_ZIG_C22H12	22	-0.14	-0.14	-0.13	-0.13
TRI_ZIG_C46H18	46	-0.06	-0.06	-0.05	-0.05

Table S8. Eigenvalues, Percentage of Variance Explained (VE) and Cumulative Variance Percentage (VA) for the first 10 Principal Components (PCs) from the Factor Analysis of Mixed Data (FAMD) analysis showing the contribution of each PC to the data variance.

PCs	<i>Eigenvalues</i>	VE (%)	VA (%)
1	34.39	41.94	41.94
2	11.02	13.44	55.38
3	8.16	9.95	65.33
4	4.41	5.38	70.71
5	3.40	4.15	74.87
6	2.84	3.46	78.33
7	2.68	3.26	81.59
8	1.92	2.34	83.93
9	1.71	2.08	86.01
10	1.46	1.78	87.80

Table S9. The 43 relevant descriptors identified through FAMD and PCA analysis, along with their corresponding acronyms. The numbers (1) and (2) next to the acronyms indicate whether the descriptor is relevant for predicting the interaction of GNFs with cell membranes (1) or with proteins (2), as determined by the RFE method. Additionally, the tool or method used to obtain each descriptor, and the type of descriptor are provided to facilitate the understanding of the descriptor and the acronyms defined.

Descriptor	Acronym	Tool/Method	Descriptor type
Surface area	SA_DMOL3M ¹	DMol3	Molecular
Binding Energy	BE_DMOL3M ^{1,2}	DMol3	Molecular
Total energy	TE_DMOL3M ^{1,2}	DMol3	Molecular
Cavity volume	CV_DMOL3M ^{1,2}	DMol3	Molecular
Dielectric energy	DIE_DMOL3M ^{1,2}	DMol3	Molecular
Solvation energy	SE_DMOL3M ^{1,2}	DMol3	Molecular
HOMO energy	HOMOE_DMOL3M ^{1,2}	DMol3	Molecular
LUMO-HOMO energy	LUHO_E_DMOL3M ¹	DMol3	Molecular
Molecular area - vdW area	MA_VDWA_SD ¹		Spatial
Shadow Area: XY Plane	SA_XY_SD ¹		Spatial
Molecular volume - vdW volumen	MV_VDWA_SD ¹		Spatial
Principal moment of inertia Z	PMIZ_SD ¹		Spatial
Radius of gyration	RG_SD ¹		Spatial
Principal moments inertia - magnitude	PMIM_SD ¹		Spatial
Shadow area fraction: ZX plane	SAF_ZX_SD ¹		Spatial
Shadow area fraction: YZ plane	SAF_YZ_SD ^{1,2}		Spatial
Shadow length: LY	SL_LY_SD ^{1,2}		Spatial
Solvent surface occupied volume	SSOV_AVS ¹		Atom Volumes - Surfaces
Connolly surface area	CSA_AVS ¹		Atom Volumes - Surfaces
Connolly surface occupied volume	CSOV_AVS ^{1,2}		Atom Volumes - Surfaces
Solvent Surface area	SSA_AVS ¹		Atom Volumes - Surfaces
Atom count	AC_AD ¹		Atomistic
Total molecular mass	TMM_AD ^{1,2}		Atomistic
Number of carbon atoms	nC ^{1,2}		Atomistic
Number of hydrogen atoms	nH ¹		Atomistic
Molecular surface area	MSA_VAMPE ¹	VAMP	Electrostatics
Total Energy	TE_VAMPE ^{1,2}	VAMP	Electrostatics
Heat of Formation	HF_VAMPE ^{1,2}	VAMP	Electrostatics
Mean polarizability	MP_VAMPE ^{1,2}	VAMP	Electrostatics
Electronic energy	EE_VAMPE ^{1,2}	VAMP	Electrostatics
Octupole xzz	OXZZ_VAMPE ^{1,2}	VAMP	Electrostatics
Octupole yzz	OYZZ_VAMPE ^{1,2}	VAMP	Electrostatics
Octupole yyy	OYYY_VAMPE ¹	VAMP	Electrostatics
Octupole xyy	OXYV_VAMPE ^{1,2}	VAMP	Electrostatics
Dipole x	DX_VAMPE ^{1,2}	VAMP	Electrostatics
ZDO Dipole x	ZZDOD_X_VAMPE ^{1,2}	VAMP	Electrostatics
HOMO eigenvalue	HOMOE_VAMPE ¹	VAMP	Electrostatics
Dipole z	DZ_VAMPE ¹	VAMP	Electrostatics
Quadrupole yz	QYZ_VAMPE ^{1,2}	VAMP	Electrostatics
Octupole yzz	OYYZ_VAMPE ^{1,2}	VAMP	Electrostatics
Total Energy	TE_FE ¹	Forcite	Energetics
Non bond energy	NBE_FE ¹	Forcite	Energetics
Van der Waals energy	VDWE_FE ¹	Forcite	Energetics

Table S10. Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) applied to the Cell Membrane Interaction model using the Random Forest algorithm, with subsets of features ranging from 3 to 25 descriptors, 50 bootstrapping repetitions, and an optimal ensemble of 200 trees. The model evaluation metrics include *Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)*, *R-squared (R^2)*, *Mean Absolute Error (MAE)*, and their corresponding standard deviations (*RMSE SD*, *R^2 SD*, and *MAE SD*). The optimal selection of descriptors is marked with an asterisk (*).

Variables	<i>RMSE</i>	R^2	<i>MAE</i>	<i>RMSE SD</i>	R^2 SD	<i>MAE SD</i>
3	0.0731	0.5840	0.0492	0.0237	0.2113	0.0170
4	0.0698	0.6230	0.0471	0.0231	0.1895	0.0163
5	0.0681	0.6375	0.0459	0.0227	0.1848	0.0151
6	0.0661	0.6584	0.0439	0.0237	0.1796	0.0145
7	0.0647	0.6706	0.0428	0.0233	0.1743	0.0138
8	0.0641	0.6767	0.0420	0.0223	0.1706	0.0133
9	0.0634	0.6847	0.0414	0.0225	0.1666	0.0131
10	0.0638	0.6838	0.0416	0.0221	0.1648	0.0130
11	0.0634	0.6886	0.0413	0.0221	0.1636	0.0130
12	0.0625	0.6946	0.0409	0.0215	0.1634	0.0128
13	0.0630	0.6923	0.0413	0.0220	0.1681	0.0133
14	0.0620	0.7022	0.0407	0.0216	0.1612	0.0129
15	0.0620	0.7001	0.0406	0.0218	0.1641	0.0132
16	0.0619	0.7030	0.0403	0.0216	0.1609	0.0125
17	0.0621	0.7026	0.0408	0.0225	0.1667	0.0135
18	0.0622	0.6992	0.0408	0.0223	0.1675	0.0133
19	0.0615	0.7074	0.0404	0.0221	0.1638	0.0134
20	0.0617	0.7053	0.0405	0.0223	0.1668	0.0133
21	0.0620	0.7023	0.0406	0.0219	0.1655	0.0131
22	0.0617	0.7047	0.0406	0.0219	0.1618	0.0133
23	0.0617	0.7056	0.0407	0.0217	0.1605	0.0130
24	0.0609	0.7116	0.0401	0.0218	0.1630	0.0132
25	0.0611	0.7127	0.0404	0.0212	0.1573	0.0130
43 *	0.0602	0.7179	0.0399	0.0214	0.1573	0.0132

Table S11. Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE) applied to the Protein Interaction model using the Random Forest algorithm, with subsets of features ranging from 3 to 25 descriptors, 50 bootstrapping repetitions, and an optimal ensemble of 50 trees. The model evaluation metrics include Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), R-squared (R^2), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and their corresponding standard deviations (RMSE SD, R^2 SD, and MAE SD). The optimal selection of descriptors is marked with an asterisk (*).

Variables	<i>RMSE</i>	R^2	<i>MAE</i>	<i>RMSE SD</i>	R^2 <i>SD</i>	<i>MAE SD</i>
3	0.1129	0.8377	0.0880	0.0348	0.1110	0.0278
4	0.1109	0.8496	0.0874	0.0349	0.1054	0.0300
5	0.1040	0.8732	0.0825	0.0292	0.0734	0.0254
6	0.0962	0.8868	0.0757	0.0223	0.0609	0.0187
7	0.0933	0.8962	0.0745	0.0230	0.0527	0.0202
8	0.0914	0.8993	0.0727	0.0201	0.0506	0.0170
9	0.0894	0.9000	0.0709	0.0212	0.0518	0.0179
10	0.0898	0.8985	0.0712	0.0213	0.0528	0.0179
11	0.0884	0.9015	0.0701	0.0198	0.0509	0.0168
12	0.0871	0.9044	0.0692	0.0202	0.0490	0.0171
13	0.0876	0.9043	0.0694	0.0191	0.0472	0.0159
14	0.0875	0.9038	0.0692	0.0191	0.0477	0.0160
15	0.0884	0.9013	0.0700	0.0203	0.0490	0.0170
16	0.0879	0.9029	0.0697	0.0196	0.0471	0.0168
17	0.0883	0.9033	0.0701	0.0193	0.0465	0.0158
18	0.0879	0.9035	0.0695	0.0189	0.0464	0.0161
19	0.0883	0.9017	0.0698	0.0186	0.0464	0.0157
20	0.0874	0.9044	0.0696	0.0198	0.0470	0.0166
21	0.0882	0.9035	0.0698	0.0191	0.0454	0.0159
22*	0.0866	0.9063	0.0685	0.0180	0.0443	0.1465
23	0.0873	0.9048	0.0689	0.0188	0.0453	0.0155
24	0.0869	0.9063	0.0686	0.0189	0.0449	0.0157
25	0.0878	0.9044	0.0689	0.0186	0.0453	0.0150
43	0.0881	0.9042	0.0695	0.0199	0.0457	0.0158

Table S12. Evaluation metrics (Root Mean Square Error – RMSE, R-squared -R², Mean Absolute Error – MAE) for the Cell Membrane and Protein Interaction model using Random Forest. The optimal model was selected using the smallest value of RMSE.

Model	<i>mtry</i>	<i>RMSE</i>	<i>R-squared</i>	<i>MAE</i>
Cell Membrane Interaction	10	0.05090	0.79573	0.03545
	12	0.05153	0.79127	0.03627
	14	0.05168	0.79255	0.03647
	16	0.05188	0.79376	0.03654
Protein Interaction	3	0.08061	0.91962	0.06674
	5	0.07853	0.92215	0.06401
	7	0.07852	0.92262	0.06425
	9	0.07945	0.92127	0.06490
	11	0.07873	0.92191	0.06436

Figure S1. ESP – electrostatic potential – predicted using ω B97X/def2-TZVP electronic structure for six different GFNs, selected considering sizes, shapes and edges. Color code: blue, white and red correspond to ESP varying from 22.0 to -22.0 kcal/mol (the scale bar is represented in the left); the red and cyan dots correspond to ESP surface maxima and minima, respectively. The GFNs backbone structure is depicted in magenta.

Figure S2. Docking results for (1) 1i1b and (2) 2hi4 proteins with three graphene flakes as ligands: HEX_ZIG_C24 (magenta), RECT_zz2ac2_C16 (orange) and TRI_ZIG_C22 (cyan). Panel (a) representing protein-ligand contacts for 1i1b protein with HEX_ZIG_C24 graphene flake, (b) with RECT_zz2ac2_C16 graphene flake and (c) with TRI_ZIG_C22 graphene flake. Panel (e) representing protein-ligand contacts for 2hi4 protein with HEX_ZIG_C24 graphene flake, (f) with RECT_zz2ac2_C16 graphene flake and (g) with TRI_ZIG_C22 graphene flake.

Figure S3. Representation of the model plasma cell membranes built to run COSMOPerm calculations and the four types of lipids – dmpc, dopc, popc and sopc – considered in this work. Color code: red representing the water molecules placed outside the lipid membrane; blue representing the polar heads and grey representing the non-polar chains of the lipids.

Figure S4. Free energy, ΔG , profile through the four membrane types considered in this work – DMPC, DOPC, POPC and SOPC –, measured at the center of the membrane, energy expressed per number of carbon atoms.

Figure S5. Prediction of (1) free energy ΔG , (2) diffusion, (3) entropy and (4) permeability through (a) DMPC, (b) DOPC, (c) POPC and (d) SOPC membranes for a total of 11 graphene flakes, sampling different shapes, edges and sizes.

Figure S6. Prediction of (a) free energy ΔG , (b) diffusion and (c) permeability measured at the center of the membrane (dmpc, dopc, popc and sopc) for a total of 40 graphene flakes, sampling different shapes, edges and sizes, sorted by shape (HEX, RECT and TRI) and by number of carbon atoms in each shape type.

Figure S7. Prediction of (a) free energy ΔG , (b) diffusion and (c) permeability measured at the center of the membrane (DMPC, DOPC, POCP and SOPC) for a total of 16 RECT graphene flakes, all of them having two graphene rings along the armchair edge (ac2) while varying the number of rings along the zigzag edge – from 2 to 32 –, sorted by (largest) size, in Å.

Figure S8. Scree Plot of Principal Components (FAMD): Percentage of Explained Variance.

Figure S9. Bar plot of loadings in absolute values, ordered from most to least influential. Each bar represents a variable, and its length corresponds to the magnitude of the loading in the respective Principal Component (PC). The dashed line indicates the threshold value (0.65 for PC1, 0.5 for PC2 and PC3, 0.45 for PC4, and 0.35 for PC5). Grey bars represent variables that exceed the defined threshold.

